

crystallisation from acetone gave shining crystalline plates (m. p. 64°). The compound gave negative tests of all classes of compounds. Its stability, negative reactions with bromine water and KMnO_4 suggested its saturated nature. It was identified as *n*-hentriacontane by mixed m.p. and co-chromatography with authentic sample. IR and NMR data further confirm its identity as *n*-hentriacontane.

The residue from eluates (ii) on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol (1:1) yielded white flakes m.p. 199°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 87^\circ$ (CHCl_3), its acetate, m.p. 237°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 80^\circ$ (CHCl_3). It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard reaction and Nollers' reaction for triterpene. Mixed m.p. determination and co-chromatography with authentic sample confirmed it as β -amyrin.

The residue from eluates (iii) yielded another colourless compound, crystallising from methanol: ethylacetate (1:1), m.p. 136-7°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 31^\circ.0$ (CHCl_3). It gave positive Salkowski and Liebermann-Burchard reactions for sterol and was identified as β -sitosterol by mixed m.p. and co-chromatography with authentic sample.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", CSIR, New Delhi, 1956, p. 77.
2. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", 1933, III, 1678.
3. "The Wealth of India", CSIR, New Delhi, 1950, II, 346.

Synthesis of Pyrazolyl Schiff Bases

SUNDAR RAO & A. S. MITTRA*

Mayurbhanj Chemical Laboratory Ravenshaw College,
Cuttack-753 003.

Manuscript received 11 April 1977, revised 29 August 1977,
accepted 24 November 1977

SCHIFF bases have gained prominence as pharmacologically important substances. They have anticancer or antituberculostatic activity¹. Anticancer schiff bases² have been prepared by the condensation of aniline with substituted benzaldehydes. Pyrimidine schiff bases^{3,4} were synthesised as possible anticancer agents. A careful literature survey revealed that no such schiff bases have been investigated in the pyrazolone series. In view of the marked pharmacological importance of this class of compound we thought it would be of interest to investigate the schiff bases having a pyrazolone nucleus. 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one on fusion with acetamide followed by alkaline hydrolysis and subsequent acidification yields the 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one. Ethanolic solution of the methyl ketone when heated with

aniline affords the schiff base. The formation of the schiff base has been confirmed by a single step synthesis involving the fusion of 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one with acetanilide at 200-20° for 6 hr. The identity of the two products obtained by the two different methods was established from the analytical values and mixed m.p. The I. R. absorption spectra of the two products were superimposable.

In the present communication 24 schiff bases were prepared using *o*-, *m*-, *p*- substituted aniline, benzidine, *m*-phenylene diamine, glycine, sulphadiazine and sulphaguanidine. In the case of *o*-nitro aniline no condensation product was obtained even though the reaction was carried out for 12 hr. in the presence of fused sodium acetate. Failure of the *o*-nitro aniline to undergo condensation is possibly due to the extremely weak basicity and steric hindrance. The formation of schiff bases have been proved from the following observations: (i) Failure to react with characteristic carbonyl reagents and therefore indicating that the ketonic group present in acetyl pyrazolone must have reacted with the amino groups of the compounds under reference, (ii) Positive test with ethanolic ferric chloride solution indicating the presence of a free $\geq\text{C}-\text{OH}$ group (keto-enol tautomeric form of >C=O at position 5).

Experimental

1. *Synthesis of 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one*: It was prepared as per our earlier method⁵. m. p. 58°, yield 60%.

It was soluble in aq. sodium hydroxide and gave colouration with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

2. *Synthesis of schiff base*: 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole and in the case of diamine 0.02 mole), aniline (0.01 mole), ethanol (20 ml) were heated on a water bath for 4 hr. On cooling the product that separated was filtered. Crystallisation from ethanol yields the shining pale yellow crystalline schiff base from aniline, m. p. 189°, yield 60% (Found: C, 74.11; H, 5.54; N, 41.21% $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ requires; C, 74.22; H, 5.84; N, 41.43%).

Condensation with the substituted aniline, amino acid, diamine, benzthiazole sulphadiazine and sulphaguanidine were carried out exactly by the above procedure. The m. p. and analytical values are given in Table 1.

3. *Synthesis of schiff base (one step synthesis)*: An intimate mixture of finely powdered 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (3 g.) and acetanilide (3 g.) was heated to 200-20° in an oil-bath for 6 hr. The dark coloured liquid was allowed to cool overnight. It was then treated with ethanol and allowed to stand for 96 hr. The solid thus obtained was filtered and washed with hot water to remove unaltered 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and acetanilide and finally

NOTES

TABLE 1—CONDENSATION PRODUCTS DERIVED FROM 1-PHENYL-3-METHYL-4-ACETYL-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONE

Sl. No.	Amino compounds used	Time of reflux in hrs	Formula of the product	m.p. °C	Yield %	Found N	% S	Calcd. N	% S
1.	Aniline	4	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	189	60	14.21	—	14.43	—
2.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	4	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	173	58	12.81	—	13.08	—
3.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	4	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	164	56	12.79	—	13.08	—
4.	<i>p</i> -Phenetidine	5	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	198	55	12.31	—	12.53	—
5.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	4	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	168	60	13.54	—	13.77	—
6.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	4	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	153	57	13.51	—	13.77	—
7.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	4	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	161	54	13.49	—	13.77	—
8.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	4	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ OCl	177	56	12.63	—	12.92	—
9.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	4	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ OCl	172	53	12.66	—	12.92	—
10.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	4	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ OCl	157	52	12.69	—	12.92	—
11.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	4	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ OBr	187	57	11.12	—	11.35	—
12.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	4	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	197	53	16.41	—	16.66	—
13.	<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	4	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	184	51	16.37	—	16.66	—
14.	<i>p</i> -Amino Phenol	4	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	274	54	13.71	—	13.68	—
15.	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	5	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	262	52	12.32	—	12.53	—
16.	Anthranilic acid	5	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	216	52	12.35	—	12.53	—
17.	alpha-Naphthylamine	4	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	167	60	12.24	—	12.31	—
18.	beta-Naphthylamine	4	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	185	59	12.12	—	12.31	—
19.	Glycine	8	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	250	42	15.49	—	15.38	—
20.	2-Aminobenzthiazole	6	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS	186	47	15.84	8.95	16.09	9.19
21.	Benzidine	0.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	242(d)	70	14.59	—	14.84	—
22.	<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	3	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	232	63	16.37	—	16.66	—
23.	Sulphadiazine	8	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S	240	40	18.51	6.92	18.75	7.14
24.	Sulphaguanidine	3	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S	278	60	20.12	7.48	20.38	7.76

purified from ethanol. m. p. 189°, Yield 30% (Found : C, 74.13 ; H, 5.56 ; N, 14.23% ; $C_{18}H_{17}N_3O$ requires ; C, 74.22 ; H, 5.84 ; N, 14.43%).

Acknowledgement

We express our thanks to the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi for financial help.

References

1. J. SENGUPTA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1966, 29, 33.
2. F. D. POPP, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1566.
3. S. K. CHAKRABORTI and BARUN KUMAR DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, L, 137.
4. M. S. SHINGARE and D. B. INGLE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, LIII, 1036.
5. SUNDAR RAO and A. S. MITTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15B, 1062.

Chemical and Pharmacological Investigation of *Pogestemon placranthoides*

A. N. BEDEKAR, K. D. DEODHAR
and
R. A. KULKARNI¹

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College,
Matunga, Bombay 400 019.

Manuscript received 16 May 1977, revised 14 December 1977,
accepted 25 January 1978

THE chemical investigation of *Pogestemon placranthoides*, revealed the presence of straight chain aliphatic hydrocarbon $C_{19}H_{40}$ and three sterols β -sitosterol, stigmasterol and campesterol. The pharmacological screening of the oil obtained from bracts, gave it's LD₅₀ 550 mg/kg. The oil also exhibited significant potentiation of sleeping time induced by hexobarbitone, indicating a CNS depressant activity.

The plant *Pogestemon placranthoides* belongs¹ to family Labiatae and reported to possess² enormous medicinal properties.

The preliminary pharmacological screening of the oil, obtained from pet. ether extract of the plant, gave LD₅₀ value as 550 mg/kg i.p. The CNS depressant activity exhibited by the oil, was further substantiated by the significant potentiation of sleeping time induced by hexobarbitone.

A white low melting (m.p. 32°) aliphatic, straight chain hydrocarbon $C_{19}H_{40}$, was isolated from the oil. The identification of the hydrocarbon, was done with the help of combustion analysis and spectral data.

The chloroform extract of the plant furnished a colourless crystalline solid (m.p. 134-35°), which was identified to be β -sitosterol. The structure of β -sitosterol was ascertained by comparing the spectral data

with that of authentic sample and preparation of derivative.

Though T.L.C. showed β -sitosterol to be homogeneous in nature, mass spectrum revealed it to be a mixture of three compounds, with molecular peaks at 414, 412 and 400. The interpretation of the mass spectrum showed that along with β -sitosterol, other two compounds present were campesterol (M^+ 400) and stigmasterol (M^+ 412).

This is in agreement with the observations made by earlier workers^{3,4} that whenever these sterols co-exist in nature it is extremely difficult to separate them to mass spectral purity.

Analysis of the ash of the plant showed the presence of iron and calcium. The presence of calcium salt may be quite significant in the light of antihemorrhagic properties possessed⁵ by calcium salt and the similar activity exhibited by the plant.

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. T. R. Govindachari, Ex-Director, Ciba Research Centre, Goregaon, Bombay, for N.M.R. and Mass spectra. One of the authors (A.N.B.) is also grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a J.R.F.

References

1. HOOKER, *The Flora of British India*, 4, 631.
2. *The Wealth of India*, Vol. VIII Ph-Re.
3. S. K. TALAPATRA and S. SENGUPTA, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 1685.
4. S.K. TALAPATRA, S. BHATTACHARYA and BANI TALAPATRA, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 601.
5. S. DIVALD and M. M. JOULLIE, *Medicinal Chemistry*, A, Burger ed. (1970), 1100.

Search for Possible Anti-Protozoal Compounds in the Quinoxaline Series

G. K. MITRA and B. C. PATHAK*

Department of Applied Chemistry, University College
of Science & Technology, Calcutta-700 009, India.

Manuscript received 13 January 1977, revised 22 July 1977,
accepted 24 November 1977

QUINOXALINES having different substitutions are reported to possess wide range of antiprotozoal activity^{1,2}. Investigation on the amebicidal activity of quinoxaline 1,4-(N,N')-dioxides and its substituted compounds³, showed that the compounds were effective in acute amebic dysentery in man although none of them could be used due to toxic side effects. On the other hand many 1-substituted 4 or 5-imidazole derivatives are known to be active against *T. vaginalis*

* To whom inquiries regarding this paper should be sent.